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BARRIERS AND GATEWAYS TO PRESERVING OUR PLACE IN THE COSMOS: THE LEGAL AND GEOPOLITICAL DIMENSIONS OF PROTECTING HERITAGE SITES IN OUTER SPACE

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ABSTRACT

The current debates over the protection of outer space heritage have been intense, fascinating, and, at times, a concerning exercise in futility for those committed to safeguarding the collective history of human space exploration. While the U.S.-led Artemis Accords have highlighted the importance of protecting cultural artefacts and sites in space, problems with the interpretation of key principles of the Outer Space Treaty, such as non-appropriation, jurisdiction, and due regard, an increasing commercial presence in space, and concerns about the application of safety zones complicate the present legal landscape. This article synthesises these issues and then proposes some steps towards an optimal governance system within the current nexus of international agreements and unpredictable geopolitical circumstances. Given these tensions, outer space heritage protection should be carried out under an international legal framework that bridges space law and space archaeology principles. The article suggests a two-tiered approach to space heritage governance. First, in the long-term, a framework inspired by elements of the World Heritage Convention could provide specialised classification, identification, and protection systems considering the different types of heritage and their universal value. Second, in the short-term (because establishing such a complex legal instrument will undoubtedly be slow), and separate from the geopolitical exigencies that underpin the Artemis Accords and its rival initiative, China's International Lunar Research Station Agreement, a series of heritage-specific bi-and-multilateral agreements between the nations with objects on celestial bodies would foster targeted international cooperation. Ultimately, it is up to individual nations to show political leadership and provide a sustained commitment to safeguard humanity's collective place in the cosmos. Failure to do so will leave a troubling legacy for future generations.

KEYWORDS: Archaeology, Geopolitics, Governance, Heritage, Space Law.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Late at night on 13 September 1959, the Soviet rocket engineer, Sergei Korolev, listened in alongside mission control to the radio signals being transmitted from the *Luna 2* spacecraft. Shortly after midnight on the 14th, the signals ceased – the spacecraft had struck the Moon.² While less celebrated than *Sputnik 1* (the first artificial satellite to orbit the Earth), *Luna 2* still had history-defining implications. Upon impact, it became the first human-made object on a celestial body and, at the same time, the first extraterrestrial heritage site. Similar feats defined the following decade (commonly recognised as the space race), spurring rapid technological development – from massive launch vehicles to compact landers – and culminating in the first human steps on the lunar surface in 1969.³ Since then, numerous missions have left traces of humanity throughout the solar system, and even out into interstellar space.

Preserving humanity’s material legacy beyond Earth reveals a paradox in international space law: while the technical and fiscal hurdles for protecting heritage sites are minimal, the legal barriers are profound. Space archaeologists have mapped heritage sites, marking significant milestones in humanity’s space exploration history, while international interdisciplinary workshops have offered thoughtful recommendations on how to protect them. However, existing space treaties provide only general ground rules, not detailed regulations for managing space activities.⁴ That ambiguity exists in determining who can safeguard heritage sites and how is, therefore, not surprising.

This article examines the evolving tension between core principles of the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty [OST]) and the growing need to recognise and protect heritage sites in outer space.⁵ These themes prompt broader debates regarding the shared value of outer space heritage, the (geo)political difficulties involved in reaching agreement on what should qualify as heritage, and the challenge of ensuring the long-term stewardship of these locations, especially in light of the increasing ambitions of contemporary space-faring nations.⁶

To assess whether the current legal framework can tackle the complexities of heritage protection, this article deploys a doctrinal legal analysis, drawing on international treaties, recent policy developments, and comparative examples of terrestrial heritage governance. Part One discusses the state of the field and the definitional issues which often bedevil space law. Part Two investigates the extant international legal framework, probing the legality of heritage protection and ties to appropriation, jurisdiction, and due regard. Part Three explores suggestions for safeguarding heritage, considering whether they upend the legal order or pave the way for robust heritage governance in space.

² Harford, J. (1997). *Korolev: How One Man Masterminded the Soviet Drive to Beat America to the Moon*. John Wiley & Sons, 142.

³ Launius, R. D. (2018). *The History of Human Space Exploration: Discoveries from the Ancient World to the Extraterrestrial Future*. Thames & Hudson, 148-9.

⁴ Hanlon M. L. D. (2021). ‘Due Regard’ for Commercial Space Must Start with Historic Preservation. *Global Business Law Review*, 9, 130-56, 132. <https://engagedscholarship.csuohio.edu/gblr/vol9/iss1/6/>.

⁵ United Nations (UN hereafter). (1967). *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty [OST] hereafter). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/introouterspacetreaty.html>.

⁶ Returning humans to the lunar surface, building a Moon base, and utilising natural resources, with a view to future colonies on Mars are just some of the intentions of the United States Government and US-based private companies in space in the coming decades. Other nations and companies have their own plans for an increased presence on celestial bodies in the future. See, Baber, W. W. and Ojala, A. (2024). New Space Era: Characteristics of the New Space Industry Landscape. In W. W. Baber and A. Ojala (Eds.). *Space Business: Emerging Theory and Practice*. Springer, 3. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-97-3430-6_1.

Moreover, most heritage discourse focuses on the Moon, given that it is the most explored celestial body in the solar system (excluding Earth, of course). However, as humanity ventures deeper into the cosmos, it is necessary to expand the conceptual framework to all other areas of space that contain evidence of human activity. This article will also consider some of the challenges surrounding the potential protection of areas of celestial bodies hitherto unexplored by humans but considered scientifically important.

Ultimately, this article argues that outer space heritage protection will falter without international political will. It will not strangle State coffers, disrupt future missions, or involve specialised new technologies. Rather, it will require a specialised instrument inspired by the World Heritage Convention but tailored to the unique environment of outer space.

2. UNDERSTANDING SPACE ARCHAEOLOGY AND HERITAGE

2.1. Literature Review

Although humans have launched objects into space since the 1950s, archaeological inquiry into spaceflight artefacts emerged much later. It developed in the 1990s as an outgrowth of investigations of ship and aircraft wrecks before developing its own referent: space archaeology.⁷ By the 2000s, however, space heritage drew scant attention, in part due to infrequent space missions, but more significantly because spaceflight had slipped out of the broader public consciousness. Scholars observed a general apathy in both public and academic spheres: “the Moon is deemed too far away, both physically and mentally – and so much out of the reach of people – that it is not worth bothering about”.⁸

The rise of private space companies in the twenty-first century, with diverse ambitions, including resource utilisation, tourism, and planetary colonisation, marked a turning point, re-injecting space into the public discourse and sparking studies on the risks posed to existing heritage sites from future activities.⁹ Space archaeology was understood to be “the study of the material culture associated with space exploration”, including “space systems, spacecraft and space debris located throughout the solar system and the landing sites of robotic and crewed missions” on celestial bodies.¹⁰ The field swiftly diversified with scholars approaching heritage from various perspectives.¹¹

While early studies stressed the importance of safeguarding the cultural landscape of space, it was not until the 2010s that the OST’s legal ambiguities were recognised as barriers to heritage protection. Legal concerns soon permeated archaeological studies, while space lawyers published specialised papers on

⁷ In his 1999 article, W. Rathje termed the study of extraterrestrial artefacts and sites “exoarchaeology”, but this failed to proliferate in the wider scholarship, with the name “space archaeology” gaining popularity instead. Rathje, W. (1999) An Archaeology of Space Garbage. *Discovering Archaeology*, 108–122. For more on the conceptual leap from ship and aircraft wrecks to outer space landing sites see, Finney, B. R. (1992). *From sea to space*. University Press of Hawaii.

⁸ Spennemann D. H. R. (2006). Out of this World: Issues of Managing Tourism and Humanity’s Heritage on the Moon. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 12 (4), 356-371, 357 <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527250600726911>

⁹ Rogers, T. F. (2004). Safeguarding Tranquillity Base: Why the Earth’s Moon Base Should Become a World Heritage Site. *Space Policy*, 20, 5-6 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2003.11.001>; Spennemann, D. H. R. (2004). The Ethics of Treading on Neil Armstrong’s Footprints. *Space Policy*, 20 (4), 279-290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2004.08.005>.

¹⁰ Gorman, A. C. (2014). Space Archaeology. In Clare Smith (Ed.). *Encyclopedia of Global Archaeology*. Springer, 6493.

¹¹ Darrin, A. and O’Leary, B. (Eds.). (2009). *Handbook of Space Engineering, Archaeology and Heritage*. CRC Press. This handbook was one of the first comprehensive volumes to integrate perspectives from scientists, engineers, geologists, archaeologists, anthropologists, and historians.

heritage issues.¹² Today, a burgeoning sociolegal-archaeological discourse advocates preservation propelled by scholars such as Alice Gorman and Dick Spennemann.¹³ Yet international space law still lacks provisions for heritage, with numerous significant obstacles remaining, and viable solutions seemingly far off.

2.2. Defining Outer Space Heritage

This article understands heritage as a “process of meaning-making”, shaped by social interaction and defined by the value people assign to it. At first glance, this challenges traditional binary concepts of tangible and intangible, and natural and cultural heritage, which José Antonio González Zarandona argues “are largely incompatible with non-Western worldviews”.¹⁴ But accepting that heritage has no inherent value does not mean that we should do away with traditional binary categorisation along those lines for outer space. This stems from the reality that, despite the varied social, cultural, and geographical backgrounds of humanity, such distinctions ultimately dissolve when considering our shared achievements in space. Heritage sites on celestial bodies, though established by specific States, symbolise the collective endeavours of humankind as a whole and warrant international protection.

But a preliminary legal issue is that attempts at defining ‘heritage’ in outer space highlight a major gap in international space law: none of the five UN space treaties addresses it directly. The only indirect reference is found in the 1979 *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*’ (Moon Agreement’s) concern for “areas of the Moon having special scientific interest” and that, “consideration may be given to the designation of such areas as international scientific preserves for which special protective arrangements are to be agreed upon”.¹⁵ The symbolic declaration of the Moon as the “common heritage of mankind” has been largely rhetorical, given that the treaty has been condemned by the leading space powers to the “garbage of history” and is only ratified by seventeen States.¹⁶

As a result, defining heritage has fallen to non-state actors rather than diplomats. The U.S. nongovernmental organisation (NGO) For All Moonkind (FAM) – now a permanent observer at the UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) – defines outer space heritage as “traces of human existence, together with their archaeological and natural contexts that occur in outer space, including on the Moon and other celestial bodies” that contain “significant cultural, historical,

¹² Walsh, J. S. P. (2012). Protection of Humanity’s Cultural and Historic Heritage in Space. *Space Policy*, 28 (4), 234-243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2012.04.001>; Reynolds, J. (2015). Legal Implications of Protecting Historic Sites in Space. In B. L. O’Leary and P. J. Capelotti (Eds.). *Archaeology and Heritage of the Human Movement into Space*. Springer, 111-129.

¹³ Gorman, Alice C. (2024). Launching Archaeology into Space and What it Tells us about Life on Earth. *Australian Archaeology*, 90, 39-41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03122417.2024.2317532>; Gorman, A. C. (2019). *Dr Space Junk VS the Universe: Archaeology and the Future*. MIT Press; Spennemann D. H. R. and Murphy G. (2020). Returning to the Moon: Heritage Issues Raised by the Google Lunar X Prize. *Institute for Land Water and Society*, 1-36; Su, J. and Li, J. (2025). Toward an International Legal Framework for the Protection of Outer Space Heritage. *Space Policy* 71, 1-12, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2024.101625>.

¹⁴ Zarandona J. A. G., E. Cunliffe, and M. Saldin. (2024). A Path Well Worn? Approaches for the Old Problem of Heritage Destruction. in J. A. G. Zarandona, E. Cunliffe, and M. Saldin (Eds.). *The Routledge Handbook of Heritage Destruction*. Routledge, 3-4. For more on the definitional debates around heritage, see Bryne, D. (2008). Heritage as social action. In G. Fairclough, R. Harrison, J. Jameson, & J. Schofield (Eds.), *The Heritage Reader*, Routledge; Smith, L. (2006). *Uses of Heritage*. Routledge.

¹⁵ UN (1979). *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. (Moon Agreement) Art. 7 (3). <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties/moon-agreement.html>.

¹⁶ Tronchetti, F. (2024). Moon Agreement: Key Provisions in S. Bhat B., D. Ukey, and A. Variath (Eds.). *International Space Law in the New Space Era: Principles and Challenges*. Oxford University Press, 174.

archaeological, or other scientific character”.¹⁷ This bridges archaeology and law, and their advocacy has recently contributed to the World Monuments Fund’s decision to add the Moon to its endangered heritage sites list.¹⁸ But since both are NGO’s, these moves, although influential for public discourse, do not directly impact UN law-making.

Still, FAM’s definition establishes two key criteria for heritage status. First: contributions to humanity’s evolutionary and cosmic histories. Hundreds of lunar sites alone reflect human ingenuity and culture – affirming humans as “natural wanderers” whose exploratory drive is “deeply embedded in our evolutionary past”.¹⁹ They also embody symbolism, memorial, and shared meaning, as seen when the crew of *Apollo 11* placed on the lunar surface a golden olive branch as a symbol of peace, as well as a silicon disc featuring goodwill messages from the leaders of seventy-three nations from Earth (*Figure 1*).²⁰ Moreover, the *Apollo 15* astronauts added a commemorative plaque and Fallen Astronaut statue honouring the then fourteen space-farers who had perished during spaceflight activities (*Figure 2*).²¹ As Michelle Hanlon notes, these artefacts provide a “treasure trove of insight into human culture, ingenuity, [and] evolution”.²²

¹⁷ For All Moonkind (FAM hereafter) (n.d.) Definition of Heritage in Outer Space. <https://www.forallmoonkind.org/about/definition-of-heritage/>.

¹⁸ Kuta, S. (2025, January 15). The Moon Makes the List of the World’s Most Endangered Cultural Heritage Sites in 2025. Smithsonian Magazine. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/the-moon-makes-the-list-of-the-worlds-most-endangered-cultural-heritage-sites-in-2025-180985845/>.

¹⁹ Finney, B. R. and Jones, E. M. (1985). The Exploring Animal in B. R. Finney and E. M. Jones (Eds.). *Interstellar Migration and the Human Experience*. University of California Press, 15.

²⁰ Pearlman, R. Z. (2007, 16 November). The Untold Story: How One Small Disc Carried One Giant Message for Mankind. *Space.com*. <https://www.space.com/4655-untold-story-small-disc-carried-giant-message-mankind.html>.

²¹ Scott, D. R. (2021). Memorandum for the Record. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/static/history/alsj/a15/drsmemo20210903.pdf>.

²² Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 140.

Yet not all sites merit such status: two-hundred tons of accumulated material on the lunar surface alone, ranging from spent rocket stages to golf balls and tools, to even human organic waste, demands demarcation between culture-revealing artefacts and detritus.²³ FAM has attempted to calibrate protection levels, emphasising that characteristics of space heritage should include “a first achievement of its kind”, and “significant impact(s) on human space exploration”.²⁴ One might infer from this that a hierarchy of significance should exist to determine the degree of protection warranted for each heritage artefact or site.

The second consideration is final location. FAM highlights “symbolic markers in an extraterrestrial context that originate from and express human identity”.²⁵ While space objects testify to human ingenuity anywhere, their peak value is only brought into focus given their final location on a celestial body. Consider *Apollo 11*’s Tranquillity Base: Although it would retain a great deal of significance if it was returned to Earth, “it is its presence on the Moon that grants it unparalleled importance as an evolutionary milestone”.²⁶ This is true because any such removal would detach the artefact from its extraterrestrial context, and as a consequence, damage its historical value.

The importance of *in situ* preservation is further highlighted by the practical impossibility of removing perhaps the most significant heritage site in the solar system – the first human footprints on the Moon. For even if we wanted to, it is currently impossible to bring those footprints back without destroying them. More significantly, given that the Moon has no atmosphere, no known biological activity, limited geological activity, and generally stable temperatures, the artefacts and sites there, including the Apollo footprints, are “almost perfectly preserved”.²⁷ This is not quite the same elsewhere in the solar system, such as Mars, with diverse atmospheric and geological environments posing a risk to heritage sites and complicating preservation discourse.²⁸

²³ Gorman, A. C. (2016). Culture on the Moon: Bodies in Time and Space. *Journal of the World Archaeological Congress*, 12 (1), 110-28, 110.

²⁴ FAM *supra* note 17.

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ Siebrits, A. (2020). The Moon that Owns Itself: Exploring New Legal Avenues to Protect Cultural and Natural Heritage in Space. In A. Froehlich (Ed) *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 124.

²⁷ Reynolds *supra* note 12, at 112.

²⁸ Rotola, G. (2020). The Legal Framework Protecting Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon and In Situ Preservation. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 4.

Taken together, however, these twin pillars – contribution to humanity’s evolutionary and cosmic histories and final location – anchor outer space heritage protection. Although it is not codified into international law, in the absence of any such specialised international legal mechanism, FAM’s working definition is a necessary first step towards framing a governance system. The next step is to consider the core UN treaties and the challenges posed by the principles of non-appropriation, jurisdiction, and due regard to heritage protection in space.

3. INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW

The OST and its supplementary treaties establish a skeleton of space law through broad rules and principles, placing emphasis on States to build upon them through national legislation and internationally through bilateral and multilateral agreements.²⁹ This national emphasis is heightened by the diversification of space technologies, participants, and mission architectures since the UN treaties were drafted. Consequently, there are often interpretive differences between nations and an overarching lack of clarity regarding how States can legally manoeuvre in outer space.

When trying to establish the legal position of any space activity, Article I of the OST is the first port of call. It stipulates that “outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, shall be free for exploration and use by all States without discrimination of any kind” and that “there shall be freedom of scientific investigation” in space.³⁰ Moreover, these broad activities – exploration, use, and scientific investigation – “shall be the province of all mankind”.³¹ Stephan Hobe notes that Article I “grants certain freedoms relating to these activities”, but then the following articles “limit these freedoms” to ensure that exploration, use, and scientific investigation in outer space remain unrestricted.³² Consequently, this balancing act produces treaty-wide inconsistencies and heritage-specific complexities.

3.1. *The Non-appropriation Principle and the Paradox of Protection*

Article II of the OST establishes one of the most fundamental rules of space law: “Outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means”.³³ This was designed to prevent States from claiming territorial sovereignty beyond Earth, thus preserving free access to space.³⁴ Yet, the very act of protecting heritage sites in space contravenes that principle as safeguarding these locations inevitably requires restricting others' access to them.

To safeguard a site, States will need to impose restrictions or establish exclusion zones – actions that, in practice, amount to exercising spatial control over an area of a celestial body. This produces something of a paradox: the protection of a heritage site requires interventions that appear to mimic appropriation. As a result, a tension has emerged around how to protect heritage sites without violating Article II.³⁵

Recent U.S. efforts have encapsulated this tension. In 2011, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration’s (NASA’s) “Recommendations to Space-Faring Entities: How to Protect and Preserve the

²⁹ von der Dunk, F. G. (2020). Scoping National Space Law: The True Meaning of ‘National Activities in Outer Space’ of Article VI of the Outer Space Treaty. In P. J. Blount, T. Masson-Zwaan, R. Moro-Aguilar, and K. Schrogl (Eds.). *Proceedings of the International Institute of Space Law 2019*. Eleven Publishing International, 229.

³⁰ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. I.

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² Hobe, S. (2009). Article I. In S. Hobe, B. Schmidt-Tedd, and K. Schrogl (Eds.). *Cologne Commentary on Space Law: Volume 1: Outer Space Treaty*. Carl Heymanns Verlag, 27.

³³ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. II.

³⁴ Dolman, E. C. (2001). *Astropolitik: Classical Geopolitics in the Space Age*. Frank Cass, 8.

³⁵ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 143-4.

Historic and Scientific Value of U.S. Government Lunar Artefacts” (NASA’s Recommendations) outlined technical guidelines for preserving the historical integrity of the Apollo landing sites. This guidance included forming exclusion boundaries of up to 2.0-kilometres, no-contact rules, and mobility restrictions. NASA’s rationale for such measures was driven by concerns from future spacecraft kicking up lunar regolith (sandblasting) to collision risks and biological contamination. However, since the recommendations were primarily focused on technical guidance, they ignored the legal ramifications of their protocols.³⁶

As the U.S. Government attempted to place NASA’s Recommendations on a legal footing, the 2020 “One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act” instructed NASA and other relevant Federal agencies to make compliance with the recommendations a prerequisite of future cooperation with the agency in lunar activities.³⁷ The Act raised concerns about the impact that the growth of commercial space actors and the increasing number of countries acquiring the ability to land on the lunar surface might have on existing U.S. sites. Its overarching aim was to “limit harmful interference to the Apollo landing site artefacts”.³⁸ Yet both instruments exemplify unilateral action: they bind only those voluntarily working with NASA and therefore cannot create legal obligations for other States.³⁹ And, while these instruments received bipartisan support in Washington, international critics have argued that even well-intentioned restrictions could amount to “*de facto appropriation*”, since they limit the free access guaranteed under Article I.⁴⁰

The U.S.-led Artemis Accords, while not a legally binding treaty, attempted to ease this concern by including a specific provision for protecting “historically significant” space heritage “in accordance with mutually developed standards and practices”.⁴¹ Section 11 of the Accords promotes the idea of safety zones as areas wherein “notification and coordination will be implemented to avoid harmful interference”.⁴² Safety zones can be understood as “keep out areas” to protect security or other relevant interests. Some commentators have suggested that these safety zones, generally associated with large-scale space activities such as resource extraction, could work for heritage.⁴³ However, these zones are temporary, “ending when the relevant operation ceases”, whereas heritage sites require permanent protection.⁴⁴ As such, the Artemis Accords reproduce the paradox rather than resolve it: they endorse the need for protection, but their temporary safety zones are ill-suited to the indefinite protection required for heritage sites. Thus, the framework for safety zones for space heritage needs to be independently configured.

³⁶ NASA (2011). *NASA’s Recommendations to Space-Faring Entities: How to Protect and Preserve the Historic and Scientific Value of U.S. Government Lunar Artifacts* (NASA’s Recommendations hereafter) https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/617743main_nasa-usg_lunar_historic_sites_reva-508.pdf.

³⁷ U.S. Congress. (2020). *One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act*. Public Law 116-275, 134 STAT. 3358. Section 3 (a) <https://www.congress.gov/116/plaws/publ275/PLAW-116publ275.pdf>

³⁸ Ibid, Section 2 (12) (b) (1).

³⁹ Su and Li *supra* note 13 at 1.

⁴⁰ Persoz, G. (2020). One Small Step to Protect Human Heritage in Space Act as One Small Step Towards U.S. Dominance? The Case for a Multilateral Treaty Protection Regime. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 48-9.

⁴¹ NASA, (2020). *The Artemis Accords: Principles for Cooperation in the Civil Exploration and Use of the Moon, Mars, Comets, and Asteroids for Peaceful Purposes* (Artemis Accords hereafter) Section 9 (1). <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Artemis-Accords-signed-13Oct2020.pdf>

⁴² Ibid, Section 11 (7).

⁴³ Gilbert, A. Q. (2023). Implementing Safety Zones for Lunar Activities under the Artemis Accords. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 10 (1), 103-111, 104 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2022.12.007>; Stubbs, M. (2021). The Legality of Keep-out, Operational, and Safety Zones in Outer Space. In C. Steer and M. Hersch (Eds.). *War and Peace in Outer Space: Law, Policy, and Ethics*. Oxford University Press.

⁴⁴ NASA, *supra* note 41 at Section 11 (7) (c).

Safety zones may well be the way of the future, but until an international framework allows protection that does not equate to appropriation, heritage governance in outer space will remain legally ambiguous. The non-appropriation principle forbids sovereignty, but heritage protection requires stewardship. In the long-term, bridging this gap is a pivotal legal challenge.

3.2. *Ownership and Jurisdiction without Territory*

If the non-appropriation principle defines what States cannot claim in outer space, Article VIII of the OST delineates what they do retain: “jurisdiction and control” over their registered space objects. This means that ownership rights of space objects are “not affected by their presence in outer space or on a celestial body”. At face value, this provision empowers heritage protection: a launching State can enforce safeguards over its craft, landers, or rovers. However, when those objects come to rest on a celestial body, a profound legal tension arises – States retain ownership and jurisdiction over them, but the areas upon which they rest are beyond national ownership and cannot be subjected to appropriation of any kind.⁴⁵

A further issue is that while jurisdiction and control focus on space objects, the legal status of intangible heritage, such as footprints and rover tracks, is unknown. In fact, these areas do not enjoy any protection in international space law whatsoever.⁴⁶

Private ownership complicates this landscape further. Russia’s 1993 sale of its *Lunokhod 2* lunar rover and its *Luna 21* Spacecraft to the American entrepreneur Richard Garriott showed that ownership of a space object can be transferred even when it sits on a celestial body.⁴⁷ Under Articles VI and VII of the OST, however, the State of registry continues to bear international responsibility and liability for those objects, and this also includes preservation.⁴⁸ Garriott, as a private owner, might appeal for conservation, but, in this case, enforcement falls to the Russian State. As commercial space activity proliferates, such problematic dualities between ownership and responsibility will only increase.

There is a terrestrial analogue for heritage protection in areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ) – the Antarctic Treaty System (ATS). The 1959 Antarctic Treaty mirrors the OST’s ethos of a non-jurisdictional space, yet the 1991 *Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty* (Madrid Protocol) operationalises multilateral heritage safeguards.⁴⁹ Like outer space, Antarctica is a *res communis*, yet the Madrid Protocol enables the designation of “Historic Sites and Monuments (HSM’s)” to be preserved collectively, regardless of the nationality of the expedition that created them.⁵⁰

However, a key challenge of the ATS remains the slow pace of designating new HSM’s, alongside tensions between scientific activity, preservation, and legislating. For instance, despite being adopted in 2005, Annex VI to the Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty (Liability Annex) for addressing environmental emergencies is still not operational.⁵¹ The ATS’s slow pace has drawn concern over its adaptability to Antarctic tourism and offers a cautionary lesson for space heritage governance.

⁴⁵ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. VIII.

⁴⁶ Spennemann *supra* note 9 at 286.

⁴⁷ David, L. (2010, 22 March). Privately Owned Soviet Moon Rover Sparks Space Law Talks. *Space.com*. <https://www.space.com/8073-privately-owned-soviet-moon-rover-sparks-space-law-talks.html>.

⁴⁸ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 145.

⁴⁹ UN. (1959). *The Antarctic Treaty*. <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/volume%20402/volume-402-I-5778-English.pdf>.

⁵⁰ UN. (1991). *Protocol on Environmental Protection to the Antarctic Treaty* (Madrid Protocol). <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/Volume%202941/volume-2941-A-5778.pdf>.

⁵¹ Madani, Z. (2025). Unpacking Inclusivity of the Antarctic Treaty System amidst Contemporary Challenges. *Polar Science*, 43, 1-11, 9 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polar.2024.101144>.

Considering the gradual expansion of general outer space activities year upon year, any analogous system must operate far more swiftly.⁵²

Without a cooperative mechanism for space heritage, its governance will remain obscure. While states may own the artefacts they have left behind, they do not control the surrounding areas. As in Antarctica, effective stewardship hinges on nations' ability to safeguard heritage for all humanity: a) without asserting ownership and b) speedily.

3.3. *Interpreting Due Regard*

Article IX of the OST requires States to conduct their space activities “with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other State Parties” while avoiding “potentially harmful interference” with another State’s activities.⁵³ However, the contours of due regard are undefined in the treaty, nor are they comfortably understood by the international community. Thus, there exists much debate around the application of due regard in space. For operational space objects, due regard means keeping an appropriate distance to avert direct or indirect interference.⁵⁴ Non-operational heritage objects warrant a similar wide berth. At present, there is enough room on celestial bodies for States to give a very wide berth to other space objects. But this is not a long-term luxury: U.S. and Chinese ongoing lunar programmes plan numerous landing sites on the lunar south pole over the next decade, sparking congestion and coordination concerns.⁵⁵ With some of those future landings likely qualifying as human heritage, it is necessary to establish a system to prevent any harm, accidental or otherwise, from occurring.

Conversely, it has been suggested that non-operational objects cannot be harmed and could be returned to Earth.⁵⁶ Although it may be possible to retrieve smaller objects, as previously discussed, the cultural significance of heritage artefacts is tied to their final location. Removing them, in the context of preserving the cosmic element of humanity’s evolutionary history, constitutes cultural and/or ethical damage. Additionally, this argument is irrelevant to the first footprints or rover tracks, as these cannot be moved. While debris removal is an important part of the move toward a sustainable future in space, this cannot occur before a thorough heritage classification system is implemented to differentiate between heritage and detritus. Also, it may well be within the purview of a future framework to clarify the contours of due regard for space heritage.

This is because, despite the temptation to turn to Earthbound analogues such as the *UN Convention on the Law of the Sea* (UNCLOS) for interpretive guidance on the meaning of due regard, this does not provide the clarity needed for the outer space context. UNCLOS stipulates that freedom of the high seas “shall be exercised by all States with due regard for the interests of other States in their exercise of the freedom of the high seas”.⁵⁷ Unlike the OST, the UNCLOS has been litigated before an international tribunal: in the case of the Chagos Marine Protected Area arbitration (*Mauritius v. United Kingdom*) in 2015. The tribunal declined to find “any universal rule of conduct” and that the convention “does not impose a uniform obligation to avoid any impairment of Mauritius’ rights; nor does it uniformly permit the United

⁵² Barr, S. (2021). How We Talk About Antarctic Cultural Heritage. *Antarctic Affairs*, 8, 33-52, 44 <https://antarcticaffairs.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/03-DIC-2021-AA-ENG-3.pdf>.

⁵³ OST *supra* note 5 at Art. IX.

⁵⁴ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 144.

⁵⁵ Feng, Y., Pengshuo, L., Haoteng, L., Liu Y., Mengrong, X., Wang, R., Chen, S., Tang, P., Cao, Y., Huang, Q., You, Q., Liu, S., Ye, Z., Yusheng, X., Xu, X., Wang, C., Jin, Y., Liu, S., Xie, H., . . . Tong, X. (in press). Navigating the Lunar Frontier: One Hundred Landing Sites at the South Pole for Future Mission Challenges. *Science Bulletin*, 2 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2025.08.035>.

⁵⁶ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 146.

⁵⁷ UN. (1982). *Convention on the Law of the Sea*. Art. 87 (2) https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf.

Kingdom to proceed as it wishes”. Instead, “the extent of the [due regard] required” depends upon “the nature of the rights held ... their importance, the extent of the anticipated impairment, the nature and importance of the activities contemplated” and “the availability of alternative approaches”.⁵⁸

The main takeaway from this interpretation is that due regard requires a balancing act. And, inevitably, as Hanlon notes, this will produce results “on a case-by-case basis”.⁵⁹ For the outer space context, this is no good. Although there may be differences between the level of protection afforded to certain heritage locations, and, in turn, this may well influence the characteristics of due regard for such sites, given the longstanding difficulty of interpreting the OST, a clearer and more consistent understanding of due regard is required as part of a future governance system for heritage protection.

4. DUAL-TRACK GOVERNANCE FOR SPACE HERITAGE

This section explores pathways towards a governance framework for space heritage protection – one that reconciles the OST's inherent contradictions with prevailing geopolitical tensions. The optimal way to do this is through a dual-track strategy: a dedicated space heritage convention in the long term, complemented in the short-to-medium term by heritage-specific state-led agreements, which can be enacted more swiftly because the UN's law-making processes are “convoluted and slow”.⁶⁰

4.1. Long-term Governance: A Space Heritage Convention?

Designing a governance regime for outer space heritage requires balancing the universal value of heritage and the non-sovereign character of the space environment. The optimal way to preserve outer space heritage sites over the long term would be to create an international convention in the spirit of the *Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage* (World Heritage Convention [WHC]): the WHC ensures the “identification, protection, conservation, presentation and transmission to future generations of the cultural and natural heritage” on Earth.⁶¹ However, most terrestrial heritage sites reside within national territories, so their mechanisms do not map onto outer space.

The first step in this framework is establishing a legal definition of outer space heritage. As established, FAM's definition of cultural heritage provides a strong foundation. However, their definition notably omits the distinction between cultural and natural heritage.

For natural heritage, it is necessary to protect the “unique and interesting geological features” on celestial bodies which accrue significant scientific and historical value.⁶² For example, robotic missions to Mars have discovered potential evidence of past habitability, which, in turn, has led to calls to recognise areas of “outstanding universal geoheritage” on the Red Planet.⁶³ This “exogeoconservation” advocates for the creation of safeguards to protect areas like the Gale Crater (a giant Martian crater thought to have once been a freshwater lake).⁶⁴

⁵⁸ Mauritius v. United Kingdom (2015) 2011-03, para 519.

⁵⁹ Hanlon *supra* note 4 at 147.

⁶⁰ Farsaris, A. E., (2020). How to Preserve Humanity's Lunar Heritage. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 82.

⁶¹ UNESCO. (1972). *Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage* (World Heritage Convention), Preamble <https://whc.unesco.org/en/conventiontext/>

⁶² Fletcher, C., van Kranendonk, M., and Oliver, C. (2024) Exogeoconservation of Mars. *Space Policy*, 68, 1-11, 2 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2024.101627>

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Evans, B. (2025, 12 September). If Life did Ever Exist on Mars, these Five Regions are our Best Bet of Finding Proof. *BBC Sky at Night Magazine* <https://www.skyatnightmagazine.com/space-science/where-find-evidence-of-life-on-mars>

Protecting these scientifically and historically valuable areas is important because as humanity expands into space, it is necessary to further scientific and educational insights into the evolution of the solar system. If such areas are not protected from potentially disruptive activities, such as resource extraction or the creation of permanent habitats, that would indefinitely alter those landscapes, then an important aspect of the solar system's natural history could be damaged.

This inevitably brings heritage into confrontation with current space plans. Although this article is not suggesting that the extraction of natural resources from celestial bodies or the creation of human bases should be prohibited, there should be areas of celestial bodies, and not just those hosting evidence of past human activity, where such activities are restricted. These spatial restrictions could take practical guidance, or at least inspiration, from ecological zoning for habitat protection on Earth. Ecological zoning works by sorting valuable spaces into protection zones wherein certain land-use restrictions and industrial controls are imposed on activities that may degrade habitats.⁶⁵ Such zones are not just mere planning exercises. Rather, they are policy instruments whose effectiveness depends on the strength of the supporting mechanisms, the will of governments, socio-economic conditions, and continuous monitoring and adjustment.⁶⁶ A space heritage convention must be receptive to the natural environment of outer space, commercial interests, and be carefully monitored by governments to keep pace with technological advances that may challenge existing protection methods.

This is to avoid falling into the same trap as the Moon Agreement with regard to future human activities in space. Indeed, in an attempt to regulate the potential exploitation of lunar resources, Article 11 declared the Moon as “the common heritage of mankind”.⁶⁷ The central issue with this provision is that it modified the traditional regime applicable to ABNJ. Traditionally, these areas, while open to free exploration and use by all States, cannot be appropriated. But when an area is labelled as the common heritage of mankind, “States can no longer explore and use it freely, but their activities must be undertaken in accordance with the rules of an international regime”.⁶⁸ This provision is a key reason for the limited ratification of the treaty.

This serves as a valuable precedent for international lawmakers today. Establishing provisions for heritage protection in a way that significantly limits commercial activities on celestial bodies would surely see it rejected by the major spacefaring nations. Instead, a heritage convention should identify areas which are to be protected from human activities (of any kind) but avoid determining how the rest of the celestial bodies can be used.

Once definitions of cultural and natural heritage in space are established, the next step is the implementation of an effective identification, nomination, and classification criterion. For this process, inspiration can be taken from the WHC. For heritage located on Earth, the process begins with a State compiling a nomination dossier, which is then assessed by the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS).⁶⁹ Once accepted, the World Heritage Committee (which meets annually) assesses and formally adds new sites to the World Heritage List.⁷⁰ At the same gatherings, the Committee also monitors the condition of existing sites. Like the ATS, this process has received criticism for being slow –

⁶⁵ Li K., Yan X., Hou Y., Lv B., Huang Y., Liu J., Han H., and Li X. (2024). Can Ecological Zoning act as an Environmental Management Tool for Protecting Regional Habitat Quality: Causal Evidence from the National Key Ecological Function Zone in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 1-12, 2 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.143623>.

⁶⁶ Ibid, 10.

⁶⁷ Moon Agreement *supra* note 14 at Art. 11.

⁶⁸ Tronchetti *supra* note 16 at 171-2.

⁶⁹ UNESCO. (1977). *Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the World Heritage Convention*, 9, <https://whc.unesco.org/en/guidelines/>.

⁷⁰ Ibid.

sometimes taking five or more years – but it is rigorous, aiming to prevent blanket protection, which a future space heritage list will need to replicate.

For space heritage, a council for processing nominations and overseeing the inscription of sites should be comprised of representatives from State Parties to both the OST and the WHC. But there will be some operational modifications as for a site to be added to the World Heritage List, the State on whose territory it rests must provide consent, which, of course, is complicated by celestial bodies being an ABNJ.⁷¹ In keeping with the OST, the probable mechanism through which a site in space would be considered for heritage protection would be the “ownership of objects launched into outer space” as afforded by Article VIII of the OST.⁷²

The identification criterion could be established using the UN’s “outstanding universal value” concept.⁷³ Of course, the concept implies that to be inscribed onto a list, the sites’ characteristics must be outstanding globally. This invariably requires a comparative analysis, evaluating a site’s characteristics in relation to others. Such a process would have to push past the nationalism inherent in space activities in that State activities often enjoy an inflated national significance, but that does not necessarily scale to outstanding universal value.⁷⁴

Andre Siebrits has proposed a hierarchy of value for cultural heritage sites and artefacts. He also points out that space heritage sites are “necessarily mixed heritage sites” that equally combine cultural and natural value.⁷⁵ UNESCO provides a provision for mixed cultural and natural heritage “if they satisfy a part or whole of the definitions of both cultural and natural heritage”.⁷⁶ While it is recognised that human activities from impactors to robotic landers and human landings qualify as cultural heritage, and that certain unexplored or partially explored areas of celestial bodies qualify as natural heritage, Siebrits suggests that only through a mixed heritage provision can the footprints and rover tracks on the Moon be practically considered and categorised as heritage. Further, to avoid blanket protection, it has been suggested that candidate sites and artefacts be divided into three groups (crewed landers, robotic landers, and impactors) of varied significance (firsts, routine, and debris) using the concept of outstanding universal value as a benchmark.⁷⁷ From this, it may well be the case that only those considered most significant will be afforded international heritage status and protection in order to avoid a level of mass protection that would restrict others’ access to areas of celestial bodies in a way that tangles with the OST’s free access.

The trickiest part of the process is the protective measures. Indeed, the most likely protective framework will feature specialised zones, adapted from the temporary safety zones in the Artemis Accords, to enable indefinite protection. However, organising such safety zones for cultural and mixed heritage will require significant technical work. For instance, the distance of the zones will vary depending on the size, location, and attributed universal significance of a site.

⁷¹ Martin, A. (2020). The ‘Outstanding Universal Value’ Concept of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention: Food for Thought to Preserve Lunar Artifacts. In A. Froehlich (Ed.). *Protection of Cultural Heritage Sites on the Moon*. Springer, 55.

⁷² OST *supra* note 5 at Art. VIII.

⁷³ UNESCO *supra* note 61 at Preamble.

⁷⁴ Lixinski, L., Lossier, M. M., and Schrieber, H. (2021). Envisioning a Legal Framework for Outer Space Cultural Heritage. *Journal of Space Law*, 45 (1), 1-45, 25. https://hannaschreiber.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Lixinski_et_al_space_heritage_intl_law_PUBLISHED.pdf.

⁷⁵ Siebrits *supra* note 26 at 124.

⁷⁶ UNESCO *supra* note 69 at 22.

⁷⁷ Siebrits *supra* note 26 at 124.

For natural heritage sites, there will need to be a distinction made between sites that should remain open for scientific research and those that should have restricted access to preserve their historical value. This is tricky because separating the scientific value from the historical value is more complicated than it first appears. The very essence of the historical value of a particular location in the solar system is often realised through scientific enquiry.⁷⁸ Thus, preventing scientific access to certain areas, especially as human technology continues to become more sophisticated and capable of returning more significant insights, is unlikely to be welcomed by the scientific community. It is for such reasons that protecting natural heritage in outer space is far more obscure than cultural.

4.2. *Short-to-medium term Protection: Heritage-specific Agreements for Space Heritage?*

While a heritage convention is the ideal long-term governance framework for space heritage, as any international lawmaking is slow, creating such a complex treaty is likely to take a long time. Furthermore, the UN has not adopted a new space treaty in decades, with the current trend showing a preference for soft law instruments. In the short-to-medium term, then, since only a handful of States have landed objects on celestial bodies, heritage-specific bilateral and multilateral agreements between States are a more feasible solution, increasing dialogue between States and recognising the importance of safeguarding space heritage. At first, agreements between the major spacefaring actors such as the U.S., Russia, China, Japan, India, and the EU should be encouraged. These could then be expanded to include other parties.⁷⁹

There are examples of these types of agreements, with one of the most recent and influential being the Artemis Accords. Although the Accords make some provisions for heritage protection, there are two overarching problems. First, it does not provide any specific details, instead advocating vaguely for future preservation in line with “mutually developed standards and practices”.⁸⁰

The second problem is that the Accords are a byproduct of geopolitical tension. Due to rivalry with the U.S., two of the main spacefaring nations (and with many sites and artefacts already on celestial bodies), China and Russia, are not signatories of the Accords, nor are they likely to be anytime soon. Instead, they have formed a similar set of initiatives: the International Lunar Research Station (ILRS).⁸¹ However, the ILRS does not mention any intention to protect heritage sites. Meaning that despite the best efforts of the Artemis Accords, existing sites are only partially, if at all, protected. While there are significant barriers to widespread cooperation between the U.S., China, and Russia, it is not inconceivable that discussions between these States that are exclusively focused on the protection of heritage sites in outer space could take place.⁸² After all, Russia and China are key members of many environmental agreements and support ecological conservation – thus it is not implausible that they could also become interested in working with other nations to conserve parts of celestial bodies and heritage sites. Such discussions may even lead to increased cooperation in other areas of space activities.

Another complication is the dramatic increase in commercial space activities. As private companies become more active and influential in outer space, their interests and operations often do not align neatly with the agendas of national governments. This growing commercial presence introduces additional layers of complexity into efforts for heritage protection, making it increasingly difficult for States to negotiate

⁷⁸ Matthews, J. J., and McMahon, S. (2018). Exogeoconservation: Protecting Geological Heritage on Celestial Bodies. *Acta Astronautica* 149, 55-60, 55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2018.05.034>.

⁷⁹ Farsaris *supra* note 60 at 82.

⁸⁰ NASA *supra* note 41 at section 9 (1).

⁸¹ China National Space Administration (2021, June). *International Lunar Research Station: Guide for Partnership*. <https://www.cnsa.gov.cn/english/n6465652/n6465653/c6812150/content.html>.

⁸² These barriers include Russia’s invasion of Ukraine and trade wars and broader ideological issues between the U.S. and China. See, Flynn, A. (2024). Star-Bound and Star-Crossed: A Path to U.S.-China Space Cooperation Through Science Diplomacy. *Astropolitics*, 22, 43-68 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2024.2368599>.

and implement effective nation-to-nation agreements since the contours of liability and responsibility for commercial companies are not straightforward. Also, the potential for conflicting commercial and political interests within a nation's space activities is likely to increase.⁸³ It is for reasons such as these that short-term heritage agreements serve as a means of encouraging a broader international effort to safeguard space heritage rather than an end in and of themselves.

5. CONCLUSION

This article has identified challenges and opportunities with respect to the protection of outer space heritage. The main legal concerns are definitional uncertainty, questions over how to grant protection to sites without violating the OST, and uncertainty over the meaning and application of due regard. On the one hand, the international community cannot protect cultural heritage sites without the explicit consent of the State that owns the space object. On the other hand, a State cannot unilaterally declare a protective zone around its heritage site on a celestial body due to the constraints placed upon it by Article II of the OST. Moreover, States must act with due regard to the interests of other States. But the provision of due regard is poorly understood by the international community, and it is unclear how it applies to the issue of heritage.

The increasingly central role of commercial actors in space exploration is also challenging the boundaries established by the OST. These include navigating regulatory gaps, as well as establishing new standards for property rights, sustainability, and resource exploitation. All of which feature prominently in the heritage debate. Indeed, the extant international legal framework cannot convincingly guide States through the tribulations of space heritage protection in the twenty-first century.

Thus, it is up to States and the wider international community to identify and instruct on space heritage protection using a variety of different approaches. This discussion has suggested a dual-track governance system for heritage. The optimal long-term solution would be the creation of a space heritage convention. But since this is the most complex solution, and considering the UN has not produced a new space treaty in decades, this article has suggested that the creation of heritage-specific agreements between States is a more feasible short-to-medium term solution. Not only would these agreements bypass slow-moving UN lawmaking levers, but they may also encourage the type of discussions between nations that are capable of penetrating current geopolitical tension, diffuse Artemis Accords versus ILRS conflict, and repair fracture lines between the leading space powers. After all, space heritage sites represent the best of humanity and showcase our collective evolutionary history.

⁸³ Dey A. and Jagadanandan J. (2025). Balancing Commercialisation and Sustainability in Outer Space: Addressing New Challenges. *Acta Astronautica*, 895-900, 898 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2025.02.010>.